

POSSIBILITIES OF ACCIDENT ASSESSMENT BY MEANS OF ROAD SAFETY AUDIT ON DIFFERENT SECTIONS OF PUBLIC ROADS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19004094>

***Annotation.** Road safety audit is a formal event of independent assessment of accident probability and safety indicators of a specific road project or transport scheme (new construction or modification of an existing road), pre-identification of dangerous sections of the road by assessing the road conditions perceived by different groups of road users through accident prevention practice.*

***Key words:** Road Safety Audit (RSA), stages of audit, management.*

Definition of RSA

A road safety audit is a formal, robust technical assessment of road safety risks associated with road transport projects.

Road safety audits:

- are completed by independent and qualified audit teams
- are completed by applying Safe System principles while seeking to ensure that roads will operate as safely as practicable by eliminating fatal and serious injury crash potential (see Sections 3 and 4)
- consider the safety of all road users (unless specified within the audit brief)
- can be conducted on proposed or existing roads.

The objective of a road safety audit is to identify foreseeable hazards for all road users. The road safety audit process provides a reasonable, but not absolute, hazard identification method for all road users with a particular focus on the reduction in fatal and serious injuries.

A road safety audit is not:

- an opportunity to redesign or make changes to a design with no apparent link to a safety issue
- a technical check on the design elements or the application of design standards (this should be carried out independently of the road safety audit e.g. as part of the design quality assurance process).[1]

Identification of road safety audit in Lithuania

As the world develops in all aspects, one of the main concerns is reducing the unnatural death rate. One of the main causes of early deaths in road accidents. About 1.3 million people die in road accidents worldwide each year, and about 50 million people are getting injured (World Health Organization, 2015). Many deaths are in low and middle income countries, though recently the accident rate has increased in developed countries as well, despite the implemented road safety instructions and legislation. The possible reason for that is the increase in the number of vulnerable road users (pedestrians, cyclists, elderly, and children) on the streets and roads.

Road Safety Audit is a detailed road safety technical inspection in all design and implementation stages, from planning to road maintenance, as well as an assessment of the

condition of the road in terms of road safety. The results of RSA are a description of the potential safety deficiencies. Usually, a list of recommendations for improvement is included in the report.

The Road Safety Audit is a highly efficient and cost-effective procedure for improvement of road safety because road safety deficiencies are identified in the design stage and instead of after the road is already constructed. As identified in the research conducted by Huvarinen, Svatkova, Oleshchenko, & Pushchina (2016) the totality of accidents causes, the audit may prevent about 27% of accidents. The prevention of such a significant amount of accidents saves justifies the costs required for the safety audit performance and implementation of the recommendations of the auditor.

Road Safety Audit identified inadequate road design solutions that could adversely affect traffic safety and be quite easily corrected. However, in the case when deficiencies are determined after the project had been implemented, i.e. when construction is done, it is very complicated and requires much investment to repair these deficiencies. Therefore, it is essential to take the appropriate decisions when designing a road at the initial stages of the project (planning, design).[2]

Figure 2. Number of road accidents, fatalities, and injuries from 2000 to 2017 in Lithuania (Lithuanian Road Administration..., 2019)

Road Safety Audit (RSA) is defined as the formal safety performance examination of an existing or future road by an independent, multidisciplinary team. It qualitatively estimates and reports on potential road safety issues and identifies opportunities for improvements in safety for all road users. To do the assessment and to give the rating to the required section this study used iRAP application. The functionalities of an iRAP can be broadly classified as crash risk mapping, star ratings, fatality estimation mapping, safer road investment plans, and performance tracking. Crash risk mapping illustrates distribution of fatalities and serious injuries on a road network based on the detailed crash data recorded. Star rating represents level of safety provided

by the given road. Fatality estimation mappings are used in investment plans to assess the benefits and costs of implementing infrastructure safety counter measures on a road. Safer road investment plans provides affordable and economically sound infrastructure options for saving lives. Finally, performance tracking uses star ratings and crash risk mapping to track road safety performance.[3]

Stages of Road Safety Audits

A complete safety audit can be conducted in three different stages. Initially at the feasibility or outline design stage, secondly at detailed design stage (the main audit) and the final audit at the pre-opening stage. A final audit can be conducted as soon as the project is complete but prior to the commissioning of the road. The 3 stages of safety audits are detailed as below.

Stage 1 - The initial audit, which is to be conducted at the very inception stage of a highway scheme. The current safety audit is conducted at this stage. Through this safety audit of the proposed roads, safety issues would be highlighted, road safety programme is emphasized, and provide specifications for inputs into the procurement document.

Stage 2 - The main safety audit (or audit of detail design) has to be carried out after the detailed design is complete. Any changes to the design arising from the audit ought to be incorporated before the project goes out for tender for construction. In case where time limitations apply, and any major changes or additions have to be carried out, it may be done by variation orders. In the main safety audit in addition to ensuring all the safety standards are maintained in the design, more comprehensive components such as detailed junction layouts, markings, signs, signals, lighting details could be closely looked into.

Stage 3 - A final audit should be made after completion of the works and prior to the opening of new highway. This is for checking signings, road markings, and placement of road furniture, as a fine tune measure.[4]

Management of Road Safety Audits

This section provides a concise and practical illustration of how RSAs (and other tools) ‘fit’ within a policy framework and project cycles in a road safety strategy. It recognises the Safe System thinking as a major shift in road safety management, road transport management, road design and traffic management (Austroads 2017a, 2017b, 2017c). As RSAs are one of the most well-known and widespread road safety processes, integrating Safe System thinking into audits is a critical step in ensuring the design and implementation of forgiving road and roadside infrastructure with a safe and credible operating speed environment for any road transport network or initiative.[5]

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